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Abstract

The Russian invasion of Ukraine triggered large-scale displacement and placed refugee children at elevated risk for trauma exposure, disrupted schooling, and long-term psychosocial distress. Estonian schools received Ukrainian students amid acute national anxiety and limited prior experience hosting large numbers of war refugees. This mixed-methods study examines Estonian teachers' attitudes toward trauma-informed care and their planned classroom responses for welcoming Ukrainian refugee students. Participants (N = 63) were teachers and education students enrolled in a trauma-focused course delivered through Fulbright support in spring 2022. Pretest and posttest results from the Attitudes Related to Trauma-Informed Care Scale for Education (ARTIC-35) showed statistically significant gains across five domains, with medium-to-large effect sizes. Qualitative analysis of end-of-course writing assignments emphasized emotional and physical safety, trauma literacy and neurobiology, modeling of regulation, and concrete classroom tools to support belonging and learning. Findings support embedding trauma-

informed preparation in educator training and ongoing professional development, especially in crisis-driven migration contexts.

Keywords: trauma-informed education, refugee students, Ukraine, Estonia, teacher training, ARTIC-35

Introduction

The Russian invasion of Ukraine has triggered one of the most significant refugee crises in recent history, with “one in four Ukrainians have been displaced and nearly four million have left their country” (Javanbakht, 2022, p. 1). In 2022, Estonia received 121,464 Ukrainian refugees with children, representing 23.2% of the 28,235 individuals granted temporary protection (European Commission, 2022). By early 2023, 66,142 individuals had stayed, while 55,322 had moved on to other destinations.

While refugee experiences are heterogeneous, they share many psychological impacts (Hodes, 2023). Refugees are “(a) civilians without self-protection resources, exposed to military and war trauma, (b) have repeated cumulative exposure to such trauma, (c) endure immense personal, material, psychosocial, literal and symbolic losses, including of family members and loved ones, homes, socioeconomic standing, and memories among others, (d) sustain cumulative psychosocial stress, economic hardship, and lack of resources during the flight, and years after displacement. War-related stress continues through exposure to news and worries about family members remaining in conflict areas, all contributing to “high levels of psychological impact” (Javanbakht, 2022, p. 2).

These cumulative experiences place refugees at high risk for long-term psychological distress, including mental health disorders, including PTSD, anxiety, and depression (Javanbakht, 2022), creating unique challenges in adjusting to new environments (Barrett & Berger, 2021). To

mitigate these impacts, immediate and culturally sensitive interventions, such as mental health first aid, psychoeducation, and assistance with navigating host-country healthcare systems, are crucial (Javanbakht, 2022).

Children and war

War disproportionately affects children, leaving enduring psychological and developmental consequences that extend far beyond other disasters. Unlike natural catastrophes, war destabilizes entire communities for generations, through prolonged conflict that subjects children to violence, threats to physical safety, forced relocation, and limited access to necessities (Shelashka, 2025). The scale of displacement is staggering. Over two million Ukrainian children crossed into neighboring countries, while an additional 2.5 million were internally displaced within Ukraine (Kruszewska & Lavrenova, 2022).

Children face the most severe mental health consequences of war, often losing access to education, safety, and stability, factors critical to healthy development (Kruszewska & Lavrenova, 2022). Nearly 44% of children in Ukraine show signs of potential PTSD, characterized by difficulty concentrating, increased emotional reactivity, isolation, and difficulty sleeping (President of Ukraine, 2024). These symptoms result from direct and indirect stressors such as bombings, displacement, and family separation, which contribute to chronic stress (Shelashka, 2025). The complex trauma experience follows what researchers term the “Triple Trauma Paradigm” (Switchboard, p2), defined as pre-flight, flight, and displacement, and resettlement.

The impact extends beyond individual children to family systems, as children frequently share adverse experiences with their parents and remain deeply perceptive of adult distress (Javanbakht, 2022, p. 2). Research indicates that up to half of refugee children may exhibit elevated levels of PTSD and anxiety (Javanbakht, 2022). Exposure to multiple traumas increases the

likelihood of mental health issues and cognitive impairments, including learning delays (Sullivan & Simonson, 2016), with effects persisting into adulthood (Slone & Peer, 2021).

Educational settings reveal the practical manifestations of these trauma responses. Educators have observed trauma symptoms among refugee children, including hoarding, aggression, and social withdrawal (Szente et al., 2006). A systematic review by Perfect et al. (2016) of 83 studies confirmed that students exposed to severe or cumulative trauma face heightened risk for cognitive dysfunction, behavioral challenges, and academic failure. These patterns were found to be true for Ukrainian children in Estonia.

Ukrainian children in Estonia

In a recent study, Toros et al. (2024) conducted interviews with Ukrainian refugee children living in Estonia. The findings revealed significant psychosocial challenges. For example, more than half of the children reported worse living conditions in Estonia compared to Ukraine. They described overcrowded and inadequate housing, the discomfort of sharing space with strangers, and anxiety due to unfamiliar environments and language barriers. Language barriers contributed to social isolation, limiting children's ability to connect with Estonian peers and confining them to relationships with only other Ukrainian speakers.

Participants also reported negative attitudes from Russian-speaking locals and expressed fears of bullying, further exacerbating their sense of alienation (Toros et al., 2024). In addition, homesickness emerged as a central theme, with children missing their physical homes, personal belongings, friends, and family members left behind. These feelings of loss contributed to sadness and anxiety, complicating their adjustment to daily life in a new country (Toros et al., 2024, p. 4). Lastly, the children participants expressed a desire for psychological support and interest in learning emotional regulation and communication strategies (Toros et al., 2024).

Attending Estonian schools

Children who enrolled in Estonian schools encountered many difficulties. These included “unfamiliarity with the language, lack of comfortable communication, changes in the times that school is on, and age and class mismatches compared to the Ukrainian educational system (Kravchenko & Strömpl, 2024, p. 224). Despite these trying circumstances, Ukrainian children reported a high satisfaction with Estonian schools. Kravchenko and Strömpl (2024) explored the experiences of Ukrainian children in Estonian schools. While exploring school satisfaction, students reported a 3.7 out of 5 rating for their school, higher than their Estonian peers, who rated it 3.3 out of 5. Students also noted caring teachers. A total of 70% of Ukrainian students reported having caring teachers, compared to only 51% of their Estonian peers (Kravchenko & Strömpl, 2024).

Schools and community-based care

Hodes (2023) highlighted the importance of a safe, supportive environment and advocated for a socio-ecological perspective to meet these multiple needs, including contextual, community-based care. One such community is schools. Schools are uniquely positioned to serve as hubs for refugee adjustment and healing. Educators play a pivotal role in supporting the resettlement and academic success of refugee students and their families (Nagasa, 2014; Szente et al., 2006). Chafouleas et al. (2016) argue that schools are ideal environments for fostering recovery in students affected by trauma. However, despite this potential, many educators report feeling ill-equipped to meet the complex needs of refugee students. In the UK, for example, only 40% of teachers reported feeling prepared to support children with mental health needs, including those coping with trauma and grief (Lowry et al., 2022). Cwirynkalo et al. (2024) studied 684 Polish teachers and found critical deficits in their readiness to work with Ukrainian refugee students. They

concluded that psychological and pedagogical knowledge is “crucial for recognizing students’ difficulties and emotional needs and developing their socio-emotional competencies, including coping skills” (p. 3). Without proper training, teachers cannot adequately “address their safety needs, and recognize and cope with their emotions, including fear, loneliness, and a sense of loss” (p. 2).

Teachers and Secondary Trauma

The consequences extend beyond individual students. Educators can become profoundly impacted when students share experiences of daily hardships and traumatic events. The DSM-5 clarifies that “indirect exposure to trauma can lead to the development of impairing symptoms” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). While teachers typically demonstrate significant compassion for their students, they may also feel overwhelmed and helpless when addressing student suffering. These feelings can result in emotional withdrawal, compassion fatigue, and secondary traumatic stress stemming from exposure to firsthand trauma accounts (Hodgkins, 2019; NCTSN, 2022; Thomas, 2013; Yang, 2021), which can lead to depression, feelings of professional incompetence, and burnout, thereby increasing teacher attrition rates (Fearson & Duncan, 2024). Training should be included at the beginning and throughout their career to develop the skills and competencies needed to support traumatized children (Fearson & Duncan, 2024).

Trauma-Informed Practices

The effects of traumatic situations and events can be mitigated through protective factors. “Studies indicate that war-affected families can repair, grow, and pass down their adaptive capacities to the next generation, which makes psychosocial support especially crucial for war-affected children to strengthen their resilience” (Denov et al., 2019). One way to mitigate is through trauma-informed practices implemented in schools.

Trauma-informed practices are methods that apply understanding of trauma's effects to establish safe, supportive environments that foster recovery and avoid causing additional harm (Ko et al., 2008). Trauma-informed teaching practices take into account how trauma affects students' learning, development, and overall well-being, and include preparing educators and school staff with the skills needed to effectively support these students (Record-Lemon & Buchanan, 2017).

Trauma-informed practices in schools are increasingly validated by empirical research. Berger et al. (2021) found that trauma-informed interventions lead to greater staff awareness, increased student engagement, higher referral rates for students in need, reductions in disruptive behavior and suspensions, and lower levels of post-traumatic stress and depression among youth. In response to such findings, this study implemented the Trauma-Informed Schools Project (TISP) model, drawing on the collective recommendations of educators, theorists, and experts in traumatology and attachment.

While the effects of trauma can be profound and enduring, they are not irreversible. With appropriate psychosocial support, war-affected children and families demonstrate a strong capacity for resilience and recovery. Trauma-informed school practices offer a powerful means of supporting refugee children by fostering emotionally safe learning environments. These interventions not only enhance academic achievement but also promote resilience by addressing students' psychological and developmental needs. As Denov et al. (2019) emphasize, families can adapt and even flourish when they have access to resources that support emotional well-being and relational stability.

The term trauma-informed refers to a multidisciplinary, evolving framework that draws on the fields of traumatology, neurobiology, and developmental theory, particularly attachment and cognitive development (Berardi & Morton, 2017, 2019). It is grounded in an understanding of how

adverse experiences affect brain development, behavior, and learning, and it incorporates evidence-based strategies that support healing and growth. This approach invites educators and caregivers to examine the intersection of attachment theory and neurobiology in understanding how trauma shapes a child's experience (Morton & Berardi, 2017). Central to this framework is the process of forming secure attachments through attunement and mentoring, which lays the foundation for the development of self-regulation skills. These skills are critical for self-stabilization, a prerequisite for accessing higher-order executive brain functions (Berardi & Morton, 2019).

As children acquire these capacities, they become better able to navigate developmental tasks and continue their recovery. This progression bolsters their sense of competence and self-efficacy, both of which are essential components of resilience. By fostering secure relationships and equipping individuals with emotional regulation strategies, trauma-informed practices help lay the groundwork for long-term healing, adaptive functioning, and overall well-being (Berardi & Morton, 2019).

Trauma-Informed School Practices Framework

The Trauma-Informed School Practices (TISP) model (Berardi & Morton, 2019) guided this study. The TISP model outlines the essential knowledge, abilities, and attitudes aligned with trauma-informed teaching expertise. It draws upon trauma-informed research, incorporating recent advances in understanding the neurobiology of stress and trauma, developmental theories, and proven methods for facilitating recovery and resuming normal development. This model is designed to be both sequential and cyclical, with each stage building upon the previous one to enhance a student's capacity to engage in various tasks (Berardi & Morton, 2019). Figure 1

presents the TISP model, and Figure 2 shows the research and conceptual elements contributing to it.

Figure 1

TISP Model

Figure 2

Tri-Phasic Model of Trauma-Informed School Practices (TISP)

Course readings, activities, and assignments were designed to facilitate student / participant ability to connect, coach, and commence with all students, but with particular focus on Ukrainian refugee students.

Methods

The context and timing of this course are critical to understanding the full context of the course, the research, and the students/participants' underlying emotional mindset.

To begin, this course was supported by the U.S. Department of State Fulbright Specialist Program in collaboration with the Estonian Fulbright Commission. The course was taught both online and in person. The face-to-face seminars began on February 28, 2022, four days after the war in Ukraine started, marking the most significant conflict in Europe since World War II.

Estonia, a border country with Russia, and a country with a similar, shared history with the Ukrainian people due to occupation by the Soviet Union until 1991, meant that many Estonians saw themselves in the eyes of the Ukrainian women and children who fled to Estonia.

Ukrainians came in large numbers to Estonia. Estonians, with “no previous experience of hosting unexpected large numbers of war refugees” (Kravchenko & Strömpl, 2024, p.218), sprang into action, welcoming Ukrainians into their homes, donating clothing and household goods, and volunteering in various capacities. Many Estonians had friends and family in Ukraine or knew people who did. They met the need with generosity and kindness.

Estonians were also anxious about the possibility of a similar invasion from Russia. It is estimated that more than 80,000 Russian citizens were living in Estonia when Russia invaded Ukraine. This, along with a shared eastern border, adds to the fear that Russia would invade Estonia. Several colleagues shared they were instantly transported back to memories of rationing under the Soviet Union. Estonian citizens began gathering grocery staples and non-perishable goods, including hand-cranked radios and candles, to prepare for potential widespread power outages. Two of my students shared that they had joined the Women’s Voluntary Defence Organisation, Estonia’s state-run paramilitary defense, where they received basic military skills, firearms training, and other tactical training. Students also shared that they had created emergency plans with friends and family members, should the emergency siren system go off. Needless to say, emotional tensions were high and at times spilled over into tears during this course. However, they came to learn how to welcome Ukrainian refugee students into their classrooms with a trauma-informed approach.

Training

Over the course of the semester, the students read three books on trauma and trauma-informed care in schools. These included: *The Body Keeps The Score* by Bessel van der Kolk (2015), *The Boy Who Was Raised As A Dog*, by Bruce Perry (2017), and *Trauma-Informed School Practices: Building Expertise to Transform Schools* by Berardi and Morton (2019). In addition to the readings, the students participated in multiple activities focused on social-emotional learning and trauma-informed strategies for use in the classroom. They also earned their Psychological First Aid certification through the National Child Traumatic Stress Network. At the end of the course, the students completed two writing assignments designed to explore their understanding of trauma-informed practices: a long-term and a short-term implementation plan, and a specific plan to welcome Ukrainian refugee students using trauma-informed practices immediately. These assignments are explained below.

Participants

The participants were students enrolled in a trauma class at Tallinn University and the University of Tartu in the Spring semester of 2022. Participants were teachers, school assistants, or students pursuing a degree in education. A total of n=63 participated in this study. Their participation was voluntary.

Data collection

Data were collected at two specific points during the semester: the first day of class and the end of the semester. The data that was collected included:

- ARTIC - 35 survey for educators
- Writing assignments

This study utilized a mixed-methods approach to gain a rich understanding of Estonian teachers' attitudes and dispositions toward the inclusion of trauma-informed practices in their classrooms. The study used survey design, course assignments, and in-class activities to collect data.

Survey

The Attitudes Related to Trauma-Informed Care measure, referred to as the ARTIC Scale, was specifically chosen to capture attitudes toward trauma-informed care. The ARTIC scale captures professional attitudes toward trauma-informed care. Validated tool to measure trauma-informed care. Co-developed by Dr. Courtney Baker, Tulane University, and the Traumatic Stress Network. There are multiple versions for different environments: Schools, Human Service organizations, State agencies, etc.

I chose to administer the ARTIC 35 for Education. This tool measured professional attitudes among people working with children in school settings and in settings where trauma-informed practices have not yet been implemented.

- The ARTIC-35 tool was selected.
- End-of-course assignments.
- Writing assignments

Two writing assignments were completed at the end of the course. These two included a summative assessment in which students created a plan to implement what they learned in class, and the second focused on how they would support Ukrainian refugee children enrolled in Estonian schools. Both are described in detail.

Assignment #1: The trauma-informed Estonian teacher

Develop a plan to become a trauma-informed educator. Include a discussion about what has influenced your thinking about children/youth impacted by trauma and the needs they have.

Consider the following:

- What steps will you need to take to create a trauma-informed environment?
- What materials/resources will you need, and how will you use these?
- What practices will you implement?
- What do you need to do to prepare yourself to be trauma-competent?

These questions are not exhaustive but should guide your thinking. Write a four to five-page paper, plus an additional page for the reference list. All sources should be cited in the reference list and in the body of the paper. The paper is to follow a reflective paper model, not a research report.

Assignment #2: Response to Ukrainian Refugee Students

If tomorrow you learned you would have Ukrainian refugee students in your classroom, what would you do to prepare? What would you want to keep in mind when you enter your classroom?

Ethical considerations

Before the study was conducted, Institutional Review Board approval was received from the University of Mary Hardin-Baylor. Once approved, the application was submitted to the Tallinn University Ethics Committee, which also approved it. In addition to these approvals, the emotional well-being of my participants was also at the forefront of this research. Even before the course began, I received a few emails from participants/students asking whether they could bring infant-aged children to class with them, as they were afraid to be away from their children due to the war and the threat of a Russian invasion of Estonia. To meet this need, during each class

session, participants, including me, took turns holding the babies during in-class activities so everyone could participate. I also began and ended each class session intentionally to promote emotional well-being by acknowledging the war, providing space for verbal processing, and leading exercises designed to calm the mind and body. As a group, we agreed to take frequent breaks and to honor the voices and experiences of all in the room, including comforting students when emotions came through tears. I was available before and after class for further discussion, and I provided contact information for on-campus mental health services.

Research questions

The following research questions guided this mixed-methods study:

RQ 1: What are Estonian teachers' attitudes and dispositions toward implementing trauma-informed practices, as measured by the ARTIC-35 survey?

RQ 2: How do Estonian teachers articulate their responses to having Ukrainian refugee students in their classrooms?

RQ 3: How do they plan to implement trauma-informed practices to support these students?

Research Question 1 Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that the teachers will have an average ARTIC-35 score of 5.00/7.00 or higher, thereby indicating support for trauma-informed care. This hypothesis is based on several factors. First, Baker et al.'s (2020) follow-up ARTIC validity study had a mean ARTIC-35 score of $M = 5.32$. Second, Schafer's (2019) study found that 80% of participants began the professional development seminar with a positive attitude towards trauma-informed care. This hypothesis was further informed by participants' decision to enroll in the course, and given Estonia's similar history to Ukraine and their shared historical trauma, it was hypothesized that they might have supportive attitudes toward supporting children impacted by trauma.

Findings

Quantitative Findings

Paired-samples t-tests were conducted to examine the effect of the intervention on participants' scores across five domains: Cause, Response, On-the-job behavior, Self-efficacy at work, and Reactions to the work. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Paired Samples t Test for the Difference Between Pretest and Posttest Scores

Domain	Pretest M	Pretest SD	Posttest M	Posttest SD	t	p	d
Cause	5.4105	.70097	5.9321	.62653	< .001	< .001	-.958
Response	5.7056	.79160	6.1811	.69652	< .001	< .001	-.731
On-the-job behavior	5.3678	.74224	5.9141	.71830	< .001	< .001	-.994
Self-efficacy at work	5.3157	.80111	5.8478	.70965	< .001	< .001	-.693
Reactions to the work	5.5714	.73220	6.0113	.60960	< .001	< .001	-.752

N=63. d represents Cohen's d.

The results for the first subscale, Cause, showed an increase from a pretest mean (M) of 5.41 (SD = 0.70) to a posttest mean of 5.93 (SD = 0.63), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$ with a large effect size (Cohen's $d = -0.958$). On the Response scale, scores rose from $M=5.71$ (SD = 0.79) to $M = 6.18$ (SD = .70), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$, also reflecting a large effect size ($d = -0.731$). For On-the-job behavior, the pretest mean was 5.37 (SD = 0.74), increasing to 5.91 (SD = 0.72), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$, with a substantial effect ($d = -0.994$). An increase was also observed in Self-efficacy at work, where mean scores increased from 5.32 (SD = 0.80) to 5.58 (SD = 0.71), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$, with a moderate to large effect size ($d = -0.693$), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$, with a large effect

size ($d = -0.752$). Last, Reactions to the work increased from $M=5.57$ ($SD = 0.73$) to $M = 6.01$ ($SD = 0.61$), $t(62) < .001$, $p < .001$, with a large effect size ($d = -0.752$).

These findings indicate that the intervention was associated with statistically and practically significant improvements across all measured constructs. The observed effect sizes, all in the medium to extensive range, suggest that the changes were not only statistically reliable but also of meaningful magnitude.

Qualitative Findings

Writing Assignment #1: The trauma-informed Estonian teacher

Four themes emerged from the first writing assignment: safety (both emotional and physical), neurobiology, modeling, and tools.

Safety

The responses showed that Estonian teachers are committed to providing a safe classroom where all students feel welcome. One student said, “I would have to make sure that every child in my classroom feels safe. That every child feels that they are at peace, feels loved by their peers and teacher.” Another wanted to keep their own expectations in mind, given what the child may have gone through. They said, “I have to control myself to create trust. I have to think about what I say or how I act if a child is not behaving or following our classroom rules.” Another wanted to remember the importance of not giving up on any child. They shared,

Some might be very resistant to your help, but you cannot give up. Probably everyone before you has, so you must not do it. Because the kid is perhaps so sure that you are going to quit anyway, as the others did. So they might be sitting there thinking, “I dare you to motivate me.”

Neurobiology

The students also mentioned the impact of learning about the neurobiology of trauma and how this will influence their classroom practices. One said,

This course allowed me to reflect and understand the biology of trauma. I took time to read again the books and reflect my own traumatic experiences in the childhood. I also thought about my students and parents, with whom I or my mom (who is working at the police with foster kids and family violence) have worked with.”

Another shared, “In this course I became aware of the essence of trauma, how and what parts of the human brain it affects the most, how trauma survivors may react in different situations and what I can do to help as a person and as a teacher.” One student reflected on the importance of listening to and believing the child. They said,

As an adult, it is so common to minimize the meaning of a child’s brief, horrific trauma experiences, and when these actions take place, not to realize that in the future they could lead to severe problems at home, in kindergarten, at school, and in public places. The belief in children’s resilience is widespread (Perry & Szalavitz, 2016), and that is why every education system needs trauma-informed educators.”

One student commented that “becoming a trauma-informed educator requires from the teacher ability to see forest behind the trees (the saying in Estonia, in English it is different). You cannot think that a child’s behavior is a child’s nature.

Modeling

Last, several shared activities or how to model social-emotional strategies to support student self-regulation. One student said,

Doing short physical activity with the students, like Starfish jumps, will help my students. Students in my class are young and very energetic. Many of them have ADHD symptoms. Short, physically challenging activities in between lessons can really help them regulate their focus and release steam.”

Modeling behavior, including how to manage big emotions, was the focus of another student’s submission. They shared,

Practicing modeling calm behavior as a class teacher is important. This is a challenge I need to practice every day and probably for the rest of my teaching career. It is so important for a teacher to stay calm and collected. Children who have trouble controlling their emotions NEED an adult by their side who can control their feelings.”

Tools

Another student planned to create a sensory station in their classroom or in a shared space at the school. They said, “Having kinetic sand or sensory rice stations somewhere in our school will support the social-emotional needs of our students. This station needs to either have its own room (maybe the calm down room).”

Writing assignment #2 end of course - Response to Ukrainian Refugee Students

This assignment yielded two themes: physical and emotional safety and connection. One student shared,

For the refugee students my first plan would be to make them feel welcomed and create a safe classroom atmosphere for them. I would choose two or three Estonian students from the class who could be the little helpers for the refugee students. They would try to answer the refugee’s student’s questions and help them around in the building. I sincerely hope

that the Estonian students and their parents would be able to help to gather some school supplies and clothes for the new kids.

Three additional students shared their thoughts for connection and inclusion. One said, “It is very important to try to build with them a healthy relationship and safe environment. They must feel that they are not outsiders and are welcome into this society.” Another, “Positive interaction, acceptance, unconditional regard and kind words are very important. They must feel that they can talk with me every time if they have some concern or any information or experience that they want to share. And, “Maybe it would be good to reorganize the classroom to get more integrated with other students. And also there has to be a private place, where to be alone if it is needed for refugees.”

The last student shared a unique situation in which they were able to provide support. They shared,

I have been working in a school for children with special needs and there I had one boy who came from Ukraine due to the war. He is really young, not even old enough to attend school yet, but the school still accepted him. We as the educators involved him in all of the school work that was possible. For example, when others did math or Estonian language exercises, he was asked to put some puzzles together. We tried to involve him in all of the activities so he wouldn't feel left out. As a person who doesn't speak Russian at all I had to talk to him only in Estonian and it was such a joy to one day hear him answering to me in Estonian.

Discussion

Overall, the students scored high on the ARTIC Scale, indicating they had positive professional attitudes toward trauma-informed care for students. This could explain why the

majority of Ukrainian students felt welcome and cared for by their teachers. This is also a rationale for why trauma-informed education is critical for all school personnel. However, it is nonexistent in the majority of teacher and administrator preparation programs worldwide. As a result, “trauma management within classrooms tends to be instinctive, reactive, and based on human instinct such as compassion, empathy, and understanding” (Frearson & Duncan, 2024, p. 564). A lack of formal training in trauma and cultural competence can lead to unintentional insensitivity and inadequate support (Nagasa, 2014; Pines, 2002). Prior research has called for teacher training that included “a mix of theory and a range of strategies and techniques they could draw upon to adapt to tailor their approach to each child” (Frearson & Duncan, 2024, p. 564). While there are multiple approaches to trauma-informed training, what is important is that trauma-informed education is included in teacher and administrator preparation programs and offered as professional development throughout these professionals' careers.

Limitations

The results from this study reveal positive growth in attitudes to trauma-informed practices. However, there are a few important limitations to note. First, given the Estonian shared history of Soviet occupation with Ukraine and their actions immediately following the invasion of Russia into Ukraine to meet refugee needs, the findings are not surprising. The data were collected during the early stages of the war, over a single semester. Given these limitations, a longitudinal research study to explore the long-term implementation practices and effectiveness would be warranted. Additionally, a study exploring student outcomes would help provide a more complete picture of how trauma-informed practices may contribute to academic outcomes. Lastly, implementing this same model in a country with a similar population of Ukrainian students would help determine whether it is independent of location.

Conclusion

Meeting the needs of children who have suffered unimaginable hardships is a moral imperative. These children did not choose displacement, trauma, or loss. They are innocent victims of geopolitical conflict who deserve compassionate, practical support. Providing trauma-informed practices supports teachers, administrators, children, and families as they work together to help children transition and grow academically and socially in a new environment. Educational institutions can no longer afford to wait for the next crisis to implement these evidence-based practices. Every day without trauma-informed approaches represents a missed opportunity to transform not just individual lives, but entire communities.

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